

Closing the loop through water and heat valorisation in industrial processes – A circular economy approach.

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1. Introduction –Water and heat integration in process industry may consider hydrogen production through water valorisation and waste heat recovery [1]. Overall, energy processes produce waste that may be reused for primary fuel savings (e.g. natural gas), for instance, in combustion-based processes [2]. While process water waste can be valorised to electrolysis units. Combined savings are achieved by the production of hydrogen-enriched natural gas (HENG). With the installation of thermodynamic cycles (i.e., Organic Rankine Cycle -ORC), additional electricity may be generated. This work presents an integrated heat recovery and electrolysis system, via ORC, in a process industry plant. A customised simulation model has been developed in Modelica language and OpenModelica environment. The conceptualized system incorporates water and heat stream recirculation from a set of processes aiming to promote a closed-loop operation of the overall industrial processes, aiming a circular economy perspective.

2. Experimental – The case-study corresponds to a tile manufacturing plant in which the viability of a heat recovery system at two tunnel kilns has already been assessed based on natural gas savings and an ORC system for electricity savings. The present study aims to further assess energy savings by valorising wastewater mainly from the raw material preparation to hydrogen production. This is accomplished by also directing the electricity produced at the ORC to an electrolysis unit. In its turn, the produced hydrogen stream is injected into the combustion chambers of the tunnel kilns to produce HENG. The system-level model has been assembled applying partly of ThermoPower Library [3]. While the tunnel kiln model has already been validated in Castro Oliveira et al. [4]. In this work, the novel model development has been related to the electrolysis unit.

3. Results and Discussion - The results for natural gas savings and payback period for the project installation are represented in Table I.

Table I. Determination of natural gas savings and payback period

Natural Gas Savings						
Parcel	Initial Case (kg/h)	Improved Case (kg/h)	Energy Savings (TJ/year)	HENG Composition	Savings (k€/year)	Reduction of CO _{2,eq} Emissions (kton/year)
Kiln 1	60.90	56.40	1.66 (7.3%)	90.4% Nat. Gas 9.6% H ₂	13.91	1.89
Kiln 2	218.50	146.43	26.58 (33.0%)		222.45	
Plant	323.38	246.71	28.22 (23.7%)		236.25	
Payback Period						
Total Investment Cost (k€)			Payback Period (years)			
714.82			3.03			

4. Conclusions – The outcomes of this work consider two main aspects: i) the development of a simulation model for the assessment of integrated heat and water valorisation of industrial processes, namely for the production of hydrogen and ii) its economic and environmental viability. In respect to the first one, the work presents a Modelica language model of an electrolysis unit, compatible to be integrated with existing combustion-based and water-using process models. In respect to the second aspects, it is possible to verify an economic viable industrial application due its payback time of 3 years. The proposed strategies enable also a significant mitigation of the total environmental impacts within the plant, with a total reduction of 1.89 kton CO_{2,eq}/year.

5. References

- [1] R.R. Bora, R.E. Richardson and F. You, Resource recovery and waste-to-energy from wastewater sludge via thermochemical conversion technologies in support of circular economy: a comprehensive review, *BMC Chem. Eng.*, 2, (2020).
- [2] L. Nazari, S. Sarathy, D. Santoro, D. Ho, M.B. Ray and C.C. Xu, 3 - Recent advances in energy recovery from wastewater sludge, *Direct Thermochem. Liq. Energy Appl.*, (2018) p. 67–100.
- [3] F. Casella, ThermoPower, (2022). <https://casella.github.io/ThermoPower/>.
- [4] M. Castro Oliveira, M. Iten, H.A. Matos, Assessment of energy efficiency improvement in ceramic industry through waste heat recovery modelling, *Comput. Aided Chem. Eng.*, 50, (2021) p. 1653–1658